

Supplementary materials 2: Information page and thank you page in the Delphi survey

Round 1 – Welcome page

Instructions

Summary of task

Welcome to this Delphi survey.

The purpose of this Delphi survey is to help establish the relative importance of 406 design, conduct, or reporting items and their potential to introduce systematic error (bias) into the results or findings of in vitro studies.

The items in this survey have been identified from an analysis of 74 study appraisal tools and three focus group discussions.

The items are organised under 11 bias domains.

You will be provided with a definition of the bias domain, if appropriate some explanatory text relating to the definition, and a complete list of the items identified. The list may be fewer than 10 items or over 100, depending on the bias domain.

Next, you will then be asked how important you think each item is when it comes to introducing bias into the results or findings of in vitro studies. You will record your answer on a five-point scale of “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”.

You will have the opportunity to comment on your answer, to give the reason for your judgement or provide other feedback that you think the investigators should be aware of when it comes to understanding the relative importance of the issue as a potential biasing factor in in vitro studies.

Finally, you can also add additional items within each bias domain.

You can save and return to the questionnaire at any time.

The figure below illustrates how the list of items, agreement options, the opportunity to comment and add additional items will be presented in this survey.

1. The survey is organised so that all items belonging to the same bias domain are listed on the same page. The bias domain is given on the top of the page.
2. The question you should answer for each item.
3. The items that you should assess. Don't mind the numbers in front of the text, they are only for the analysis process.
4. Click on the eye icon to see the bias domain definition.
5. The answer options – choose one per each item.
6. You may add a comment by clicking on the speech bubble icon. Note that the comment needs to be at least 3 characters.
7. You may click on the “ADD INDICATOR+”-button if you want to add an additional item.
8. Use the “Delete” and “Edit” columns to delete or edit your added item, respectively.
9. Click the “BACK” button to go to the previous page in the survey.
10. Click the “NEXT” button to go to the next page in the survey.

Details to consider

Due to the nature of the discovery exercise, not all items are phrased in a way that directly target in vitro studies (as you will see, for example, some issues concern teeth) or may otherwise not be immediately understandable. If you think an issue would be important if it were phrased more appropriately, please indicate this in your comments.

Do not worry at this stage about whether a given item is organised under the “correct” domain, or whether a bias domain is optimally defined. The present task is to establish the relative importance of each item. The bias domains and definitions are only an organising structure to help make the presentation and analysis of items more manageable.

We recommend not spending more than an hour at a time in evaluating items. We also recommend not spending too long on a single item – because we are interested in the aggregate answers of the group, intuitive answers are sufficient.

Click "NEXT" to start the survey.

Round 1 – Thank you page

You have now completed the first round of the Delphi survey.

Thank you for your willingness to participate and for sharing your knowledge and time with us answering this questionnaire.

We highly appreciate your effort, and your contribution will be very valuable for us in the creation of the tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies. We will inform you about the results of this first round of the Delphi study when we have completed the analyses of the results.

In the meantime, if you have any questions or concerns regarding the data collected in this survey, please feel free to email the project lead, Gro Haarklou Mathisen at

Gro.Haarklou.Mathisen@vkm.no.

Round 2 – Welcome page

Information

Welcome to round 2 of the Delphi survey for identifying internal validity items important for in vitro studies.

In the first round you were asked to assess the importance of 406 items. For the items you assessed in round 1, 168 items reached agreement on their relevance for in vitro studies. None of the items reached agreement on not being relevant for in vitro studies. The remaining 238 items are included in round 2 for a second assessment.

You will be able to see your previous scoring of each item (visible as a grey box around the answer option). Also, the scoring and comments added from all participants from round 1 are visible.

See below for instructions and the setup of round 2 of this Delphi survey.

Instructions

Instruction 1: If you believe the item is not relevant for in vitro studies, please choose one of the disagreement options (strongly disagree or somewhat disagree). If you believe an item is not relevant it is really helpful to us if you leave a comment as to why.

Instruction 2: Please do not indicate your agreement based on the current wording of an item. The items on which you are giving feedback have not been designed for use in an assessment tool - we are interested in the core concept expressed by the item, and whether you agree that the concept is relevant when it comes to potentially introducing systematic error into the results or findings of an in vitro study.

Instruction 3: Due to the nature of the discovery exercise, not all items are phrased in a way that directly target in vitro studies (as you will see, for example, some issues concern teeth) or may otherwise not be immediately understandable. If you think an issue would be important if it were phrased more appropriately, please indicate this in your comments.

Instruction 4: Make yourself familiar with the new features described below before starting the questionnaire.

1. The results of the previous round will be visible. You can see them by percentage (percentage button) or by frequency (absolute button).
2. The survey is organised so that all items belonging to the same bias domain are listed on the same page. The bias domain is given on the top of the page.
3. The question you should answer for each item.
4. You can see the comments of the previous round by clicking "VIEW PREVIOUS ROUND COMMENTS"
5. The items that you should assess. Don't mind the numbers in front of the text, they are only for the analysis process.
6. Click on the eye icon to see the bias domain definition.
7. The answer options – choose one per each item. Your answer in the previous round is marked with a grey box. If you wish to edit the answer you gave in the previous round, just click the option you would like to change to.
8. You may add a comment by clicking on the speech bubble icon. Note that the comment needs to be at least 3 characters.
9. Click the "BACK" button to go to the previous page in the survey.
10. Click the "NEXT" button to go to the next page in the survey.

Remember that you can save and return to the questionnaire at any time.

Click "NEXT" to start the survey.

Round 2 – Thank you page

You have now completed the second round of the Delphi survey.

Thank you for your willingness to participate and for sharing your knowledge and time with us answering this questionnaire.

We highly appreciate your effort, and your contribution will be very valuable for us in the creation of the tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies. We will inform you about the results of this second round of the Delphi study when we have completed the analyses of the results, and you will be invited to an online workshop to have a guided discussion on items where no agreement on importance for in vitro studies has been identified.

In the meantime, if you have any questions or concerns regarding the data collected in this survey, please feel free to email the project lead, Gro Haarklou Mathisen at Gro.Haarklou.Mathisen@vkm.no.